

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DESTRUCTION OF A THICK PIPE FROM VARIABLE INTERNAL PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

Initial fracture time formula and a front movement equation in a thick pipe for the primary stage of pipeline operation associated with the injection of liquid or gas product into it, were derived. Calculated comparative curves of failure front movement show that significance of accounting of initial period of internal pressure growth compared with the case of neglect of this period and acceptance of initial constant pressure. A variant of cyclically changing internal pressure was studied. A formula of critical number of loading cycles to the primary destruction, was derived.

Keywords: scattered destruction, damageability, variable loading, destruction front, incubation period.

I. Introduction

In the paper [1], a problem of studying scattered destruction of a damaged thick pipe under the constant internal pressure, was solved. However, there are cases of appearance of emergency situation of a pipeline at the initial period of injection of liquid or gas product in it. In this connection, there arises necessity to study the process of deformation and damageability of the pipe in this period characterized by the factor of monotonous

growth of internal pressure. In this paper an attempt is made to assess the influence of this factor.

II. Problem statement

We consider a thick cylindrical pipe under the action of monotonous increasing in time and uniformly distributed pressure $p(t)$, and the external surface of the pipe is free from effort. Accept that the pipe material is isotropic and elastically – damaged. In this case, as deformation equations we accept [1]:

$$\begin{cases} \mathfrak{D}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2\mu} (1 + M^*) s_{ij} \\ \varepsilon = \frac{1}{3K} \sigma \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where ε , σ are ball portions, \mathfrak{D}_{ij} , s are deviators of stress and strain tensors:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{ii}; \quad \sigma = \sigma_{ii}; \quad \mathfrak{D}_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij} - \frac{\varepsilon}{3} \delta_{ij}; \quad s_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\sigma}{3} \delta_{ij}$$

In relations (1) the volumetric damage is neglected.

In (1) M^* is a hereditary type damage operator:

$$M^* s_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n \Phi(\sigma_i(t_k^+)) \int_{t_k^-}^{t_k^+} M(t_k^+ - \tau) s_{ij}(\tau) d\tau + \int_{t_{n+1}^-}^t M(t - \tau) s_{ij}(\tau) d\tau \quad (2)$$

where (t_k^-, t_k^+) are the intervals of damage growth time, $\Phi(\sigma_i(t_k^+))$ is a defect healing function [2].

For monotonously changing stress state, the damage operator (2) passes to an ordinary hereditary viscoelasticity operator:

$$M^* s_{ij} = \int_0^t M(t - \tau) s_{ij}(\tau) d\tau. \quad (3)$$

In conditions of complicated stress state for a damaged isotropic medium we accept the strength criterion as [1]:

$$\sigma_i + M^* \sigma_i = \sigma_0, \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_i = (s_{ij} s_{ij})^{1/2}$ is tangential stresses intensity, σ_0 is ultimate strength of a defectless material.

III. Problem solution

Since in our problem we have monotonous growth of stresses in time, the damage operator is of the form (3). Then deformation relations (1) are identical with corresponding relations of viscoelasticity theory. The stresses are determined based on the matching method and are of the form as for an elastic problem (here it is accepted that the pipe material is incompressible, $\nu = 0,5$) [2]. Accordingly, the intensity of tangential stresses will be:

$$\sigma_i = \sqrt{2}p(\tau) \frac{a^2 b^2}{b^2 - a^2} \frac{1}{r^2}, \tag{5}$$

where a, b, r are internal, external and current radii of the pipe, respectively.

According to L.M. Kachanov (3) we express σ_i by means of a unique function $\beta(t)$ of a dimensionless radius of destruction front, having accepted:

$$\frac{a}{b} = \beta(\tau); \quad \frac{r}{b} = \beta(t); \quad 0 < \tau < t. \tag{6}$$

Then for intensity of tangential stresses, we get:

$$\sigma_i(t, \tau) = \sqrt{2}p(\tau) \frac{\beta^2(\tau)}{1 - \beta^2(\tau)} \frac{1}{\beta^2(t)}. \tag{7}$$

Since the greatest value σ_i , accepts on the internal contour $r = a$, i.e. $\beta = \beta_0 = \frac{a_0}{b}$, where a_0 is the pipe's primary internal radius to the destruction, just at this place the destruction will occur for the first time. Let t_0 be an initial destruction time of the pipe's internal contour, then for $\tau < t \leq t_0$, when $\beta(\tau) = \beta(t) = \beta_0$, we have:

$$\sigma_i = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{1 - \beta_0^2} p(t). \tag{8}$$

To determine the initial failure time t_0 we substitute (8) in the strength criterion expression (4), having accepted

$$p(t) = p_0 \cdot f(t), \tag{9}$$

where $f(t)$ is a dimensional time function.

Then we get:

$$f(t_0) + \int_0^{t_0} M(t_0 - \tau) f(\tau) d\tau = g(1 - \beta_0^2). \tag{10}$$

Here it is accepted that

$$g = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{2}p}. \tag{11}$$

To obtain the failure front movement equation, we substitute (7) in strength criterion formula (4). Then we find:

$$\frac{f(t)}{1 - \beta^2(t)} + \frac{1}{\beta^2(t)} \int_0^t M(t - \tau) f(\tau) \frac{\beta^2(\tau)}{1 - \beta^2(\tau)} d\tau = g; \quad t > t_0 \tag{12}$$

For constant internal pressure $p = p_0$ and $f(t) = 1$. To estimate the influence of transitional period of injection of the product into the pipe, i.e. the growth of pressure p from zero to p_0 , we analyse the situation for the simple case, when

$$M(t - \tau) = m = const; \quad f(t) = t^\alpha; \quad \alpha > 0. \tag{13}$$

In what follows, we will consider time t dimensionless by means of the constant m and therefore we accept $m=1$. For the initial incubation period t_0 we get:

$$t_0^\alpha + \frac{1}{1 + \alpha} t_0^{1+\alpha} = g(1 - \beta_0^2). \tag{14}$$

For the failure front function we get the differential equation:

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = \frac{0,5(\alpha + t)t^{\alpha-1}\beta(1 - \beta^2)}{g(1 - \beta^2)^2 - t^\alpha}. \tag{15}$$

It should be solved for the initial condition (14). For the constant pressure $p = p_0$ ($a = 0$) we have:

$$t_0 = g(1 - \beta_0^2) - 1, \tag{16}$$

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = \frac{0,5\beta(1 - \beta^2)}{g(1 - \beta^2)^2 - 1}. \tag{17}$$

For convenience, in equations (14) and (15) we assume $\alpha = 1$, then

$$t_0 = -1 + \sqrt{1 + 2g(1 - \beta_0^2)} \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = \frac{0,5(1+t)\beta(1 - \beta^2)}{g(1 - \beta^2)^2 - t} \tag{19}$$

Since we study time interval of internal pressure increase from zero to p_0 , then for dimensional quantities $0 \leq f(t) \leq 1$ or in the considered special case $0 \leq t \leq 1$. Then from (18) we get

$$g(1 - \beta_0^2) < 1,5 \tag{20}$$

For dimensionless time mt at $\alpha = 1$, the limiting time interval will be $[0; m]$. It also follows from (18) that incubation period always holds, naturally within the limits of (20).

For the failure front movement to start, it is necessary that the right hand side of (19) be positive at time t_0 , whence we have the condition:

$$g(1 - \beta_0^2)^2 - \sqrt{1 + 2g(1 - \beta_0^2)} > -1 \tag{21}$$

Similar conditions for $p = p_0 = const$ will be:

$$g(1 - \beta_0^2) > 1 \tag{22}$$

Conditions for the existence of incubation time

$$g(1 - \beta_0^2)^2 > 1 \tag{23}$$

front failure crack starting condition.

To compare failure processes in both cases and clarify the influence of account of period of liquid or gas product injection to the pipeline, the calculations were carried out for the values $g = 2$; $\beta_0 = 0,2$. The failure front movement curves are given in fig.1. This time, for initial failure time with considering injection period, it was obtained $t_0 = 1,2$, without taking into account injection period $t_0 = 0,92$.

Fig.1. Failure front movement curves

1. Allowing for injection period. 2. Regardless of injection period.

The given curves testify on significant influence of consideration of period of filling the pipeline on its further load bearing ability.

We now consider the case of cyclic change of internal pressure:

$$f(x) = 1 + \alpha \sin \omega t \tag{24}$$

where α is a dimensionless amplitude of internal pressure change, ω is the frequency of this change.

Substituting (24) in (9) and (8), and then in failure criterion (3), allowing for the form of the damage operator (2), we get the following equation for determining the incubation period t_0

$$1 + \alpha \sin \omega t_0 + \sum_{k=1}^n \Phi_k(t_k^+) \int_{t_k^-}^{t_k^+} M(t_k^+ - \tau)(1 + \alpha \sin \omega \tau) d\tau + \int_{t_{n+1}^-}^{t_0} M(t_0 - \tau)(1 + \alpha \sin \omega \tau) d\tau = g(1 - \beta_0^2) \quad (25)$$

where g as before is determined by the formula (11).

The failure front movement equation will be of the form

$$\frac{1 + \alpha \sin \omega t}{1 - \beta^2(t)} + \frac{1}{\beta^2(t)} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n \Phi_k(t_k^+) \int_{t_k^-}^{t_k^+} M(t_k^+ - \tau)(1 + \alpha \sin \omega \tau) \frac{\beta^2(\tau)}{1 - \beta^2(\tau)} d\tau + \int_{t_{n+1}^-}^{t_0} M(t_0 - \tau)(1 + \alpha \sin \omega \tau) \frac{\beta^2(\tau)}{1 - \beta^2(\tau)} d\tau \right\} = g; \quad t > t_0 \quad (26)$$

Analyze the incubation period equation. Rewrite it in the form

$$1 + \alpha \sin \omega t_0 + \int_0^{t_0} M(\tau) d\tau + \alpha \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n \Phi_k(t_k^+) \int_{t_k^-}^{t_k^+} M(t_k^+ - \tau)(1 + \alpha \sin \omega \tau) d\tau + \int_{t_{n+1}^-}^{t_0} M(t_0 - \tau) \sin \omega \tau d\tau \right\} = g(1 - \beta_0^2); \quad (27)$$

Accept as before, that the damage operator is constant $M(t - \tau) = m = const$, then the equation (27) will be:

$$1 + \alpha \sin \omega t_0 + mt_0 + \alpha m \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n \Phi_k(t_k^+) \int_{t_k^-}^{t_k^+} \sin \omega \tau d\tau + \int_{t_{n+1}^-}^{t_0} \sin \omega \tau d\tau \right\} = g(1 - \beta_0^2) \quad (28)$$

We determine the intervals of active loading time as intervals of time of positivity and growth of additional

cyclically changing part of internal pressure: $(t_k^-; t_k^+) = \left(\frac{2\pi(k-1)}{\omega}; \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + 2\pi(k-1)}{\omega} \right)$. Taking this into account

in (28) and making integration, we find:

$$1 + mt_0 + \alpha \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{m}{\omega}\right)^2} \sin(\omega t_0 - \varphi) + \frac{\alpha m}{\omega} \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^n \Phi_k\right) = g(1 - \beta_0^2) \quad (29)$$

where $tg \varphi = \frac{m}{\omega}$.

The defects healing characterizes the function $\Phi_k(t_k^+)$ that we write in the form:

$$\Phi_k(t_k^+) = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{in the absence of defects healing phenomenon.} \\ 0 & \text{for total healing of defects.} \end{cases}$$

Assume that the defects healing phenomenon is absent, i.e. $\Phi_k = 1$. Then for t_0 we approximately accept that $t_0 = \frac{2\pi n}{\omega}$ and from (29) we find approximate value of the number of loading cycles corresponding to the incubation period:

$$n_{kp} = \frac{g(1 - \beta_0^2) - 1}{m(2\pi + \alpha)} \cdot \omega \quad (30)$$

According to (30) to small values of average pressure P_0 there corresponds finite number of loading cycles to the primary failure

$$n_{kp,0} = \frac{\sigma_0(1 - \beta_0^2)}{\sqrt{2mP_1}} \cdot \omega \quad (31)$$

where $P_1 = \alpha P_0$ is a finite amplitude of an additional, cyclically changing part of the internal pressure. Instant failure occurs for

$$P_{0,kp} = \frac{\sigma_0 (1 - \beta_0^2)}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (32)$$

The curve of dependence of n_{kp} on P_0 qualitatively is of the form shown in fig.2.

Fig.2. The curve of latent failure stage in incubation period.

This curve divides a quarter of the plane $(P_0; n_{kp})$ into the domain of realizable scattered form of failure and the instant failure domain.

IV. Conclusion.

Initial fracture time formula and a front movement equation in a thick pipe for the primary stage of pipeline operation associated with the injection of liquid or gas product into it, were derived. Calculated comparative curves of failure front movement show that significance of accounting of initial period of internal pressure

growth compared with the case of neglect of this period and acceptance of initial constant pressure.

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